

THE IDENTIFICATION OF BARRIERS TO THE FOUNDING AND OPERATION OF REUSE CENTERS OR REUSE POINTS IN MUNICIPALITIES—IS THERE ANY INTEREST IN THESE BUSINESSES?

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Abstract:

The environment is burdened with large quantities of both ordinary municipal waste and unnecessary things. Living costs are constantly rising, which causes existential difficulties for more inhabitants. This created necessary conditions for a change in behavior - to stop discarding unnecessary things and offer them to the others for subsequent use. Reuse centers and reuse points can be instrumental in improving the quality of the environment through waste prevention, and thus contributing to the resilience of society, i.e., improving the quality of people's lives by meeting their needs with used items that would otherwise end up in municipal waste or illegal dumps in the countryside. Based on the semi-structured and guided interviews with the organizations responsible for the waste management of Czech municipal authorities, barriers to the founding were identified. A basic sentiment analysis was also part of the interviews. The results show that the main barriers are not only financial expenses but also a lack of knowledge of the legal conditions of operation. There is a predominance of positive sentiment over ambivalent one; very negative sentiment did not occur.

Keywords:

environment, reuse center, reuse point, waste.

JEL Classification: O13, O44, Q56.

1 INTRODUCTION

The contemporary way of life is often referred to as the era of consumerism. People in developed countries have become accustomed to the fast availability of almost everything and take it for granted. Most products have become consumer goods. Many products are not as expensive and unaffordable as they were ten, twenty, fifty, or a hundred years ago. We are constantly renewing and improving what we wear, communication means, and cars to meet the needs of today's modern man (Pollard et al., 2016). As confirmed by Bakker, Wang, and Huisman (2014) and further by Murakami et al. (2010), declining product lifetimes have detrimental consequences for the environment. In turn, all of this produces waste, which is becoming a modern-day enemy. To ensure that the planet does not end up literally flooded with waste soon, we need to find ways of not only reducing the amount of waste but also reusing it. This is the direction in which civilization is evolving. Waste sorting, recycling, or heat recovery of what can no longer be used are some examples. There is a gradual shift away from landfills, where waste de facto ends its life cycle, and a growing effort to find alternative ways of handling waste, which is an integral part of everyone's life (Foster, 2020).

The environment can also be linked to economic functions, and the so-called unvalued or undervalued services should be included in the economy (Andersen, 2007). Sustainable development can be seen as one of the options for the development of human society, which combines both social and economic progress and full environmental protection (Pawliczek, 2011). Sustainable development indicators can be described as those whose continuous monitoring and evaluation allow tracking of a society's progress towards or away from

sustainable development. At the same time, with their help, it is possible to determine the boundaries within which the development of society will evolve (Mezřický, 2005). One of the prerequisites for sustainable development is the pursuit of environmentally friendly behavior on the part of all entities and individuals. Environmental behavior is, in a narrower sense, behavior that has a significant impact on the environment. When a person realizes the environmental impact of his or her action, one can refer to the so-called intentional environmental behavior or directly to environmental behavior (Krajhanzl, 2010).

Another, equally important, element is sustainable consumption. This can be defined as the use of services and products that satisfy the basic needs of society and improve the quality of life while minimizing the consumption of natural resources, toxic substances, waste, and pollutants during the life cycle of the service or product without jeopardizing the satisfaction of needs of future generations (Bačík & Hlaváček, 2005).

The pursuit of unlimited economic growth based on linear principles (Institute for Circular Economy, 2020) leads to serious environmental, economic, and social impacts. The principle of circular economy is the circulation of materials that become waste but do not end up having zero value in waste dumps but remain in circulation with a different value of material or energy use (Ghisellini, Cialani & Ulgiati, 2016). From the beginning, waste needs to be viewed as a raw material. There is only a low awareness of the demand for recycled materials in the Czech Republic (Geussová & Kužvart, 2020).

The waste management hierarchy is represented by a five-level pyramid that lists waste management options from the most acceptable to the least acceptable solution: waste prevention, preparation for reuse, recycling, further utilization such as waste and disposal energy recovery (Hřebíček, 2009). The international community has developed a broad consensus on the circular economy (Yu, 2011). The circular economy is defined as a concept in which there is no waste (Circular Economy Institute, 2020). The circular economy is defined by its basic principles: drawing energy from renewable and sustainable sources, closing material flows in functional and endless cycles, and designing products and services that have a positive impact on human resources and natural ecosystems (Bilitewski, 2012). A closed-loop waste management policy has been in place in Germany for more than 20 years (Nelles, Grunes, & Morscheck, 2016). In fact, Germany is considered a world leader in waste management and knowledge (Nelles & Morscheck, 2008). Zero waste is a stepping stone to sustainability. Zero waste means management practices such as minimizing waste, cleaner or reduced use of renewable resources, or green belt development (Rathoure, 2020). A zero-waste approach leads society members to ask questions about what they consume, how much they consume, and how waste affects the environment (Rafia, 2019).

Building and operating reuse centers (reuse centers or reuse points) as instruments of a sustainable economy is becoming an important element. It is an effort to reduce the amount of municipal waste and to look for other ways to reuse products. Extensive experience with the application of sustainability principles in day-to-day life as well as with the actual operation of reuse centers can be illustrated by the example of Germany (Hängebruch, 2020; Kissling et al., 2013; Matthies, Selge & Klockner, 2012). Reusing is one of the ways to eliminate waste and prolong its stay in circulation. Therefore, establishing, and operating reuse centers as instruments of a sustainable economy is becoming an important element in the current efforts to reduce municipal waste and to seek further opportunities for secondary use of products. Reuse centers can be viewed as an element of the circular economy, which is a highly relevant and crucial contemporary issue that must also be addressed at the local level of individual municipalities.

A reuse center is a place where small functional household items that would otherwise end up in municipal waste can be handed in free of charge (Tepvos, 2022). By doing so, they can serve

someone else. It is one of the easiest ways to further donate unwanted functional items. These are places where supply and demand for household equipment meet locally. There is quite a lot of public interest in this type of project. Except for reuse centers, it is still forbidden to take anything away from waste collection points, even if only for personal use (Zijememimalisimem, 2022). An item dumped in the waste collection point becomes waste, the property of the founder of the waste collection point. The founder may not transfer this waste to other people who do not have a waste management license. The main reason is environmental protection.

Reuse centers can also be used as places for projects related to the circular economy and charitable or social activities. For example, they can also offer jobs for people with disabilities, jobseekers, or otherwise disadvantaged people who find it difficult to get a job. Reuse centers can have an environmental, educational, and social character (Šálková et al., 2021).

Zelený (2018) states that only 2 organizations were founded in the Czech Republic before 2006 and that the largest number of organizations were founded in 2014 (11) and 2016 (9). In his research from 2018, this author already identified 47 reuse centers (30 centers were in the Moravian-Silesian Region at that time, followed by the South Moravian Region (20) and Prague (20)). However, the Federation of Furniture Banks and Reuse Centers (2023) currently lists 101 reuse centers, of which 86 are united in its organization. This confirms Zelený's (2018) idea that the reuse topic has become a phenomenon in the Czech Republic and is expected to undergo substantial development in the following years.

2 PROBLEM FORMULATION

The desk-research method was used as the basic method for the in-depth analysis and evaluation of the current state of knowledge, which enabled a detailed overview of the issues related to the further use of mixed municipal waste. Based on the semi-structured interviews conducted with representatives of selected municipal authorities in the Czech Republic, as a pilot phase of the research, to obtain data, the guided semi-structured interviews were subsequently conducted in September 2023 in the organizations responsible for the waste management of the selected municipal authorities in the Czech Republic.

The purpose of the interviews was:

- to determine interest in reuse centers/reuse points,
- to identify barriers to the founding of reuse centers/reuse points,
- to identify barriers to the operation of reuse centers/reuse points,
- to identify attitudes towards the issue of further management of mixed municipal waste.

The respondents were selected to include all 11 categories of municipalities in accordance with the data collection database of the Czech Statistical Office (this division of municipalities is based on the population size). At least two respondents were identified in each interval (Table 1). The sample was increased by one respondent in the interval exceeding 10% of the base sample and by two respondents in the interval exceeding 20%. The size of the sample thus determined was increased to the stage of information saturation. Information saturation refers to the way information is distributed across an attribute, i.e., the amount of information that a single attribute can carry. If a given attribute no longer provides any new information, one can speak of saturation (Horchová & Reich, 2016).

Table 1: Breakdown of the respondents by the population size

Czech Republic – interval breakdown	Percentage of the base sample	Minimum number of respondents in the interval	Real number of respondents
fewer than 200 inhabitants	1.6	2	2
200 – 500 inhabitants	6.1	2	2
500 – 1,000 inhabitants	10.6	3	3
1,000 – 2,000 inhabitants	16.3	3	3
2,000 – 3,000 inhabitants	16.6	3	4
3,000 – 5,000 inhabitants	6	2	2
5,000 – 10,000 inhabitants	9	2	3
10,000 – 20,000 inhabitants	9	2	2
20,000 – 50,000 inhabitants	12	3	4
50,000 – 100,000 inhabitants	8	2	2
100,000 and more inhabitants	22.4	4	4
TOTAL	100	28	31

Source: own processing according to the Czech Statistical Office, 2023

Based on these interviews, a basic sentiment analysis was also conducted. Sentiment analysis is a research area concerned with the analysis of people's opinions, moods, evaluations, attitudes, and emotions towards objects such as products, services, organizations, individuals, issues, events, or topics, and their characteristics (Liu, 2010). The advantage of sentiment analysis is that it can be used in both the commercial sector and state administration. On a scale of very negative to very positive, the prevailing sentiment of the municipal representatives interviewed was rated. The analysis aimed to find out how the respondents perceive the issue of waste management at the municipal level and what their attitudes are towards the options of further use of items whose life cycle can be prolonged by being put into recirculation. Positive and negative keywords associated with the issue of reuse centers and reuse points were defined.

3 RESULTS

The interviews with the representatives of 31 municipalities have revealed that only 5 reuse centers or reuse points are operated in these municipalities. Most of these businesses are linked to the municipality, most often in the form of an organization that is set up and financially supported by the municipality. Only in one case (Pilsen) a purely commercial enterprise was recorded. Most respondents have discussed the possibility of setting up reuse centers or reuse points in some form, at least more or less intensively, or at least theoretically considered this option. These were more likely to be cities, i.e., urban settlements with a larger population. In smaller settlements, the topic has usually not been discussed yet, very often due to ignorance. Although this is a subject that is topical and interesting even from the perspective of municipal representatives, there are numerous reasons why it is a rather theoretical consideration now.

The research included an analysis of the main barriers (economic, social, legal, and others) that lead to the fact that reuse centers and reuse points are not operated by municipalities. These barriers were identified during the interviews with government representatives and assigned a weight on the scale of 1–10 (Table 2). Many of the reasons why municipalities do not operate reuse centers or reuse points to date, or are not even considering doing so now, were repeated in many cases. The most frequently mentioned, with the highest weight, were the lack of suitable space, the problem of financing the establishment and operation, the lack of knowledge

of the issue, the lack of a suitable methodical procedure for founding it, the lack of knowledge of legal regulations, the problem of ensuring the operation in terms of personnel, and the risk of abuse by certain socially vulnerable groups.

Table 2: Barriers to the setting up and operation of reuse centers and reuse points at the municipal level

Reasons	Weight		
	Low (1-3 points)	Mean (4-6 points)	High (7-10 points)
economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - so far, no cost analysis has been carried out for establishing and operating a reuse collection point 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - financing operation - the expected return would not cover the cost of operation - there would be no revenue from it 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the problem of staffing (to pay the staff) - the high cost of operation - the high cost of establishment without subsidy - low municipal budget
social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - there is no interest on the part of inhabitants (mothers are interested in the exchange of children's clothes and toys, but probably not in anything else) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to guard things, to prevent theft - the existing informal system of free collection in waste collection points works well - there are no socially vulnerable inhabitants in the municipality - there is no potential for circulation of items - low potential of excluded inhabitants - attractiveness of things - only interesting things for the cottage, genuinely made - it would not be user beneficial 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - one cannot believe in the people's awareness to use reuse centers/points - people use old things until the end of their value, i.e., they throw away only the thing that is really unusable - abuse by other resellers - abuse by certain social groups - risk of professional collectors of precious metals
legal		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - they don't know what it should look like and what conditions it should meet - ignorance of the conditions of operation - ignorance of the issues - ignorance of the legal framework 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - prohibition of waste transfer to other people - potential harm, e.g., to health, by the item being handed over - lack of methodology to support the establishment and operation of centers/points - prohibition of certain items (electrical appliances)
other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inhabitants are not yet fully interested. - They haven't considered anything like this yet. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - they don't know about this possibility - there was no time to address this issue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - no suitable space is available - they do not own a plot of land or any other suitable space

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is no sorting, storing, fee system (handling fee, allowance?). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the problem with record keeping - no information on how it should be run - demanding character of administration - changes in political priorities (construction of waste collection point, composting plant, biogas plant) - it does not deal with much waste, only a per mille of the total municipal waste that is produced - sanitary reasons - e.g., the seat could not be used, sanitation would be costly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - suitable place (container, building, room?) - anticipated need for large space - lack of time to find out information - difficulty in finding a suitable person - staff - problem of unclear impact of the potentially considered deposit system for PET bottles and cans on the amount of sorted waste
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Source: own processing, 2023

Despite these existing barriers, the municipal representatives often declared their interest in the waste management issues and in finding other ways of how to reduce the amount of waste produced (most often by households). Municipalities themselves have long been trying to find different ways and possibilities to reduce the volume of mixed municipal waste. The most frequently mentioned examples of municipal waste management needs in the near future were ways to increase and improve the separation rate of sorted waste, supporting the implementation of the door-to-door system through subsidies, increasing the amount of recyclable waste to meet recycling targets, the need to introduce multi-commodity waste collection, subsidies to expand existing waste collection points and to support the creation of new ones, facilities for the utilization and processing of biowaste and gastro-waste, and working with inhabitants to teach them how to separate waste more and better (to motivate them to separate).

Other relevant circumstances arising from the guided interviews:

- Reuse plants will not eliminate too much waste - there will not be a significant reduction in bulky waste.
- There is no uniform system of sorting, storage, and fees.
- A new generation needs to be brought up with a different attitude to waste.
- There is a need for legislative support so that not so much waste is produced.
- Almost all municipalities are also interested in the social aspect of reuse sites - i.e., social entrepreneurship.
- There is a lack of consistency of political representation regarding the issues of waste management and reuse centers/points.
- There is a lack of space capacity for reuse centers. Space is limited, negotiations with owners of suitable premises are necessary, there are problems with agreements.
- Municipalities do not believe that reuse centers will really be used by socially vulnerable inhabitants, they rather expect them to be abused.
- There is concern about the heavy administrative burden, reporting, accounting, legal documents.
- There is a lack of methodology for running reuse centers/points, lack of knowledge of the issues.

- Reuse centers can generate illegal dumps (in connection with excluded groups).
- Furniture can be used as fuel and generate CO2 and emit substances associated with surface treatment into the air (stains, paints, varnishes).
- There is no centralization of the issue - ideally a linked website for the entire Czech Republic with education and good marketing support.
- Municipalities fail to sort 60% of municipal waste, they expect to pay penalties.
- The compulsory deposit for PET bottles and cans will also be a problem for the requirement to sort 60% of waste - the sorted waste component will drop significantly.

The efforts to reduce the amount of municipal waste are partly driven by the Waste Act, which stipulates that by 2025 municipalities in the Czech Republic should sort 60% and recycle 55% of municipal waste, but there is also personal interest and awareness of the importance of not wasting resources and materials that can be further used. Despite this trend, however, most respondents consider this regulation and the set threshold to be, if at all, very difficult to achieve.

Representatives of municipalities often mentioned the interest of inhabitants in reusing second-hand items. It is not uncommon to receive inquiries about the possibility of putting away still usable items for further use, inquiries about the possibility of taking away suitable selected items from the waste collection point, inquiries about spare parts for appliances, etc.

The fact that inhabitants make efforts not to discard and dispose of usable items in an irretrievable way, but, on the contrary, look for possibilities to reuse still functional and undamaged, only worn-out items, is also evidenced by the currently widespread informal variants of passing on to other interested people, which fulfil the characteristics of the circular economy. These are often virtual centers for the transfer of second-hand goods. These are usually, for example, second-hand groups set up for this purpose on Facebook, home 'garage' sales, special events organized by individuals and interest groups to share and pass on second-hand items. Freely collecting items from the waste collection point is also frequent, but it is informal and the result of the good will and efforts of the waste collection point staff to make it possible for the still usable items to find other owners. Community exchanges of used goods between people are very common nowadays (mostly children's items, toys, household goods, etc.). Various charity collections also represent a frequent way of handing over used but still functional items.

Based on the interviews with the municipal representatives, a basic sentiment analysis was also conducted to define the degree of positive or negative perception of this issue. Based on the respondents' reactions and their comments on the individual interview points, the degree of their overall attitude towards the issue of municipal waste management in terms of the reuse of suitable (preserved, undamaged, and functional) items was assessed by the individual interviewers. As shown in Table 3, most respondents had a more or very positive view of finding ways to reuse functional items, which can be considered a positive result. This forms a basis for further addressing waste management in the context of the circular economy.

Table 3 Results of the sentiment analysis based on the interviews with municipal representatives

Sentiment	Very negative	Negative	Neutral/ Ambivalent	Positive	Very positive
Prevailing sentiment		4	10	9	8

Source: own processing, 2023

Note: The term ambivalent means a positive sentiment in some aspects and a negative sentiment in others.

The main positive and negative key terms have also been defined as a result of the sentiment analysis.

Positive keywords: waste reduction, use (utility) value, social aspect, environmental protection, change in behavior.

Negative keywords: illegal dumps, inappropriate human behavior, lack of space, mandatory percentage of waste sorting.

4 RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

The conducted research may be limited by the random selection of municipalities, where the representativeness of municipalities in terms of settlement structure was observed, but not all categories in terms of the political and economic situation of the local population had to be addressed. Approaches to waste management and subsequent utilization may be different in economically weaker areas with, for example, high unemployment and different in economically stronger regions. Different perceptions of reuse sites may also be caused by the age structure of the population of municipalities or by other aspects.

5 CONCLUSION

The research has shown the interest of municipal representatives in the issue of further use of objects that may have a longer life cycle and may have another use. Similarly, there has also been recorded the interest of inhabitants, who currently rather use various informal ways of sharing used items on a social basis. On the other hand, many barriers have been identified that currently prevent the expansion and establishment of more reuse centers and reuse points. One can clearly state that most municipalities have expressed their interest in finding ways to dispose of second-hand but still functional consumer goods for their next owners among the inhabitants. The potential for reuse centers and reuse points is certainly there at present, but the crucial prerequisite is to find a way of removing the main barriers. The basis for further addressing waste management in the context of the circular economy is the prevailing positive perception of this issue.

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